

ANALYSIS OF CRASH ABSORBING ELEMENTS FOR AUTOMOTIVE APPLICATIONS

P.Bravo, E. Larrodé, J. Ullod, J.J. Alba

Department of Mechanical Engineering - ICMA
University of Zaragoza
María de Luna, 3
50015 Zaragoza (Spain)

ABSTRACT

Using composite materials, such as carbon or glass fibers, is state of the art in the modern automotive industry. More and more metal parts in cars for instance become or are already replaced by advanced materials. One of the car structures which might be produced of composite materials are crash absorbers. In the case of a crash this device has to absorb the crash energy first by reversible then by irreversible deformation. The difficulties in the application of composite materials for this task is specially their weak impact behaviour. Therefore, not only the geometry and adequate materials for example, but also the fiber-matrix system has to be chosen carefully. It even might be necessary to design the part which has to be replaced totally anew. This requires a highly involved optimization process which can only be performed effectively by means of theoretical, numerical simulations of the designed energy absorber using computer codes.

The numerical tools for the simulation of the crash of composite structures which has been developed will be discussed. These tools are in particular a finite element computer program based on a modification of the DYNA3D computer code developed by J. Hallquist at the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (USA). These routines were compared to the commercial computer program ABAQUS/Explicit of Hibbit, Karlsson & Sorensen, Inc. (USA). Material model routines were introduced in both programs. Theoretical results for the simulation of the crash of composite cylinders were found by the application of the already mentioned numerical tools, and compared to results obtained by tests which have proven that composite materials can be applied successfully in energy absorbing devices. This was shown exemplarily by means of the design of a composite crash absorber for cars.

Keywords: Energy absorption, numerical simulation, crash, composite materials.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent years have confirmed a high increase of Composite Materials in transportation industry in such way that structural components usually made of metallic materials have been replaced by non-metallic advanced materials. Aeronautical applications such as parts of wings, flaps or floors have been the prior use before to be used in transportation industry because their weight savings and high strength mainly.

Nowadays crashworthiness simulation is becoming to an efficient tool for the development of land transport vehicles. Crash simulations of all kinds of engineering structures like cars, trucks and railway cars made of steel, composite and others materials, can be achieved due to advances on numerical models simulations. Moreover, the integration of numerical and experimental studies in the transportation industry has been met in order to achieve safety and efficiency in modern car design.

Special interest from the point of view of analysis concerning global behaviour, is material characterization. Strength, toughness, and mechanical properties of composite materials in general, are so different from classical models, that new material models must be performed to have completely defined the behaviour of the material during the analysis of the problem, and must be able to develop damage and fracture evaluations (initiation, propagation, instability), and strength and toughness criteria. Once we have analyzed the failure or the damage of the material, next step consist of identification of types of damages or failures and its quantification, that is to say, the classification.

In this paper a study of the energy absorption mechanism is presented. The study is focused to the application of the results to a prototype of an absorbing element used by automobile industry. In order to save total weight the energy absorbers shall be replaced by others made of advanced composite materials in addition to be economically competitive with respect to the already existing metal devices.

One of the applications of crash simulations in automotive industry is energy absorbers, usually made of metallic materials. Those elements, in case of crash of the vehicle, must absorb the crash energy in a given speed range first by reversible then by irreversible deformation of the absorbing device. Weight and manufacture cost savings have been taking into account at the time of composite energy absorbers need to be designed. Not only the change of material but the physical effect (rolling energy, hydraulic energy, etc.) have been modified (deformation energy). Designs of energy absorbers must be feasible to be manufactured in easy way and if possible at low cost, and at the same time, the work of the absorbing element must be simple. The main function of a crash absorber is to avoid damages towards the rest of the structure, and damages in a structure are most of times related to deformation energy, then it is necessary to fit up the structure with a mechanism which be able to absorb the deformation energy. Keeping in mind that absorption energy depends on crash velocity, the speed ranges for reversible and irreversible deformation of the absorbing elements are a matter of the design. Correlation between speed and energy absorption can be seen in table 1.1.

Some significant examples in the transportation industry can be appointed. So, in automobile industry, more and more devices to avoid damages at low crash velocities not only in the bodywork but in main structure are being placed, bearing in mind safety of the occupants mainly. In aeronautical industry, a typical example studied is a helicopter crashworthiness in case of power loss when the maximum vertical velocity is 15 m/s. There are two types of energy absorbers depending on the part of the structure we are interested. So, it can be feasible to put energy

absorbers to reduce the structure damage and to reduce the accelerations that the pilot has to bear.

Deformation		
Reversible	Irreversible	
Speed range	Speed range	
0 - 4 Km/h	4 - 15 Km/h	European Market
0 - 8 Km/h	8 - 15 Km/h	North American Market

Table 1.1. Speed ranges vs. deformation energy for different markets.

In both cases composite materials are being used in order to achieve light structures, but is necessary to reduce manufacture and material costs, therefore a competitive design must be performed. Numerical simulation of the impact and crash of structures made of composite materials have been carried out in last years and have demonstrated the good agreement with experimental results. Firstly, is necessary to establish material models for composite strength and failure modes, in this case a bi-phase model has been used. Later, the structure must be calculated taking into account the new material model, and results from this structure can be compared with experimental results from testing. This simulation methodology is intended for the prediction of the crash behaviour of structures that could be subjected to it. Once the behaviour has been determined, it will allow to optimize design for crash damage and to make suitable changes, in order to prevent bad responses.

Some of the advantages of composite materials applied to energy absorbers that could be achieved are weight saving, low cost and to make easy manufacturing. In order to obtain such benefits some requirements should be satisfied. So, a minimum load level below the structure must not suffer any kind of damage; a maximum load level before failure initiation of the energy absorber start, in such way that maximum load during crash remains always below this level; and a quantity of absorbed energy, which depends on the maintenance of a high crash load and a large crash displacement.

After a great number of numerical simulations of different specimens validated with an amount of experimental testing could be demonstrated that composite materials are feasible to be incorporated in energy absorbers in order to obtain the desired objectives.

2. MATERIAL

The shock absorber is composed by several types of materials due to the necessity to have some requirements to be reached. Two important material systems are included in the design, the metallic and non metallic. So the metallic system is used in the design of the support structure, and the variety of non metallic components are used as the absorbing elements and friction devices.

Energy dissipating systems based on metallic structures have been developed last years. The energy absorbing process in these systems is the formation of plastic zones in which the metal undergoes high strains in bending and stretching. The ability to undergo extensive slip without the presence of cracks is one of the characteristics of the ductility of metals, such as mild steel and aluminum alloys. As the strain increases the slip process becomes more complicate and a higher stress is required to maintain the deformation process. The brittle behaviour appears when the material is unable to slip extensively due to the formation of cracks. Mechanical response of a metal has some influences such as alloying additions, mechanical deformation and heat treatments during the slip process.

Some aspects about the deformation of metals are also applicable to plastics, although the details are entirely different. Thermoplastics often undergo large plastic strains in tension before fracture, and thermosetting plastics fail in tension after only 2 to 6 per cent elongation. As metals, the strain rate sensitivity of plastics are related to the kinetics of motion of the molecules.

The part of the design which has been used as energy absorber is a continuous fiber-reinforced composite tube. When is subjected to crushing loads, the response is complex and depends on interaction between the different mechanisms that control the crushing process. Three crushing modes by continuous fiber-reinforced composite tubes can be appoited:

- 1) Transverse shearing.
- 2) Lamina bending.
- 3) Local buckling.

Combination of fibers and matrices as well as the structure of the tube are important parameters to the progressive crush of a composite tube so not all composite tubes will progressively crush (see refs. 1-7). Some mechanisms are able to cause catastrophic tube failures which avoid the progressive crushing. Catastrophic failures may occur, in a brittle fibre-reinforced composite tube where the length of the interlaminar cracks is less than a ply thickness or if internal cracks are quickly growing and propagating along the length of the tube.

Figure 2.1. Crushing process of fiber-reinforced composite tubes. (see ref.5)

Brittle fiber-reinforced composites exhibits exclusively transverse shearing and lamina bending crushing modes, but ductile fiber-reinforced composite materials never show these modes. Local buckling crushing mode can be exhibited by both ductile and brittle composites. A combination of the transverse shearing and lamina bending crushing modes can be exhibited by brittle fiber-reinforced composite tubes.

The influence of material (resins and fibres), geometry, laminate stacking sequences, velocity of the mechanism have been taking into account during the design stage (see refs.1-6).

A brief remark about the drawbacks of crushing of fiber-reinforced composite tubes encountered during the calculation can be given; the integrity of the structure after the shock depends on the type of resin-fiber system which it has being used, the possibility of a catastrophic failure when the design is not well done and some requirements as energy absorbed, geometrical and material parameters are very difficult to be reached.

3. DESIGN

The design basically consists of nine parts which are made of four material types, contains one internal composite tube, absorbing the energy during a crash of the car, and an external metal tube assuring well operation of the absorbing element and the stability of the structure during the tow of the car. The drawing below (figure 3.1.) shows a depicted description of the different parts as well as the material which they are made, and an approximation of the way it works can be intuited. As it can be seen the prototype consist of metallic (steel) parts 1, 3, 6, 7, 8, and 9; composite parts (fiberglass) 2, nylon 4, and rubber 5.

A tube is used in the design (number 2), which is made of fiberglass, and this is the crash absorbing device during the irreversible deformation while a crash occurs.

Figure 3.1. Prototype description and materials which are made of.

Some remarks about the way shock absorber works can be given and following figure 3.2., can be easily understood.

Reversible deformation: during a crash, parts 7, 8 and 9 move into direction of part 6, compressing the rubber material (part 5) up to 25 mm which is the maximum allowable reversible deformation of the absorber. If no more energy is introduced to the system, the rubber expands and parts 7, 8, and 9 come back to their original position.

Irreversible deformation: in the case of speeds from 4 to 15 km/h, part 7 touches part 6 and moves the structure consisting of parts 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9 against 1 which is fixed at the frame of the car, therefore destroying the composite cylinder (part 2) at the interface with part 1. The allowable irreversible deformation is 50 mm.

Interface: the interface between part 1 and 2 has an important influence since geometrical relations between these parts are decisive for the initial failure behaviour of the composite tube and therefore for assuring a force-displacement behaviour similar to that of energy absorber devices made of ductile materials.

Several designs of the interface have been studied in order to optimize the collapse of the cylinder with the objective of finding a geometrical relation which offers a force-displacement behaviour described before. Summarizing the more important design variables which have been used can be ordered as follows:

Support Structure:
Absorbing element:

- geometry, maintaining some fix dimensions
- tube length
- ratio tube diameter / tube thickness
- material configuration
- material properties (fibre, resin, percentages)
- manufacturing process

Figure 3.2. States during the shock absorber operation .

4. ANALYSIS

The numerical simulation of energy absorbers have been carried out by means finite element computer codes. Models have been run in vectorized and multi-tasked mainframe supercomputers, e.g. CONVEX and HP. Several software packages have been used for numerical crash simulations, explicit finite elements programs with interactive graphic meshing pre-processor and interactive graphic results post-processing. Numerical simulations allows to obtain new and before hard to get, high priced or impossible to reach results such as the detailed crash energy absorption histories of individual components. Descriptive pictures of particular and combined failure modes, the detailed history of the process, impossible to be perceived by human eyes or high-speed cameras, and every kind of effects that have not been able to bear in mind as supports, reinforcements etc.

The analysis of the structure can be approached subdividing the calculation according to the dominant behaviour of the part which is being studied. So, energy absorber can be divided basically in two structures, one of them, the absorbing element, has a dynamic dominant behaviour whereas the support has a static conduct mainly. Then the analyses of the prototypes have been divided in

two steps. One of this steps is related with the calculation of the support structure of the absorbing element. The other step is the dynamic analysis of the structural part which is subjected to crashworthiness.

The support has several requirements to be satisfied; one of these is to bear all the reactions transferred by the elements with dynamic behaviour. If no crash occurs, the absorber may also serve as towing device, and must have disposed a mechanism to support the bumper. But the main is to hold the components of the structure which have the role to absorb the energy by reversible and irreversible and to assure the correct work of these parts. Therefore, two complementary analysis have been carried out, a static with large deformation analysis and a dynamic analysis.

The calculation of the crash absorber has been performed using the substructure technique. Different substructures have been created to modelize the global structure, so several substructures have been necessary to discretize the support structure, and the absorbing element such as irreversible mechanism as reversible mechanism have been independently treated. Then all of them are joined to complete global behaviour of the structure.

Programs chosen for this task are DYNA3D and ABAQUS. Both contains truss, beam, shell and solid elements which handle geometric and material nonlinearities. Dynamic processes are considered by the implementation of an explicit time integration algorithm which is very fast and therefore adequate for the calculation of time dependent problems as they occur in crash simulation.

However, the analysis of composite materials is limited because the modelization of laminated plates is considered only by a homogenization procedure. Furthermore, a fracture law for dynamic processes is missing. These obstacles can be overcome since both codes are an open system and therefore manipulations of the source code by the user can be done easily (user subroutines).

Analysis of the support structure.

Support structure has been designed and calculated according to particular requirements. Main support is attached to the frame by means bolted joints, and possess a mechanism to receive loads coming from the bumper, and a rigid ring in case to serve as towing device.

The calculation of this design under a load applied with an angle of attack of 70° was performed and could be considered as good in terms of stiffness and strength. Photo 1 shows a stress and displacement mapping of the absorber under the load case described before. All the requirements were satisfied by the prototype and bad responses were not found during the calculation. Furthermore, this design has also been checked in terms of a tensile load, and stresses displacements were found to be completely acceptable

Photo 4.1. Contour of stresses on the displaced crash absorber.

Analysis of the crash absorbing elements

The analysis of the crash absorbing elements has been carried out by means the use of two finite element code, DYNA3D and ABAQUS/Explicit. These packages are explicit, nonlinear, finite element code for the transient dynamic response of three-dimensional solids and structures. Are recommended for problems where high rate dynamics or stress wave propagation effects are important. Both of them use a large number of relatively small time steps, with the solution being explicit (and inexpensive) at each step, without forming and solving the large matrix equation typical of implicit codes and does not require iteration at each step. Important time computing saving can be obtained due to the above mentioned goals. An implicit code needs often a lot of memory due to the assembly of a large stiffness matrix at each time step. These finite element codes are based on a finite element discretization of the three spatial dimensions and a finite difference discretization of time. The method used to integrate the equations of motion in time is the explicit central difference method. Automatically, the maximum time step size at each step of the solution is calculated by the codes, and the time step is adjusted in order to minimize the number of time steps used in a solution. The cost of the analysis is minimized by this characteristic moreover to assure that stability is maintained. A biphas material model was developed and introduced as a subroutine in the two codes. Some results of the calculation can be seen in figure 6.1.

5. TESTING

A great number of experimental tests have been carried out due to the difficulty to control the required parameters such as maintained load, testing velocity, etc. In photo 5.1. a view of the experimental testing can be seen.

Photo 5.1. Crash testing

Several kinds of testing have been done depending on the parameters which were trying to be controlled. An important parameter has been the design and calculation of crash initiators in order to obtain the desired force-displacement curve.

Energy absorber device crash-tests

The typical load-displacement curve for cylindrical composite tubes without any failure initiator shows a initial high load and a radical loss of load carrying ability. Inclusion of a load limiting failure initiator at one of the ends results in a loss or a reduction of the initial peak load but enhances the post failure performance. In order to obtain the best maintained load and a progressive

crash behaviour is the inclusion of triggering devices.

Three different types of crash initiators have been used in this study, as can be seen in figure 5.1, Type "a" is a chamfer which has been tested with three different angles (30, 45 and 60 degrees) in two different versions, inside and outside chamfer. Load-displacement curves are showed in figures 5.2., 5.3., 5.4. The only influence of the chamfer-angle is how quickly is reached the stable crash load. The amount of this maintained load seems to be not dependent of the angle. The results obtained with the inside and outside chamfer are very similar.

Figure 5.1. Crash initiators

Type "b" is a chamfer in the half inside or outside thickness. The used angles are 30, 45 and 60. To reach the maximum reversible load without damage is the objective of this kind of this triggering device initiator. To predict the initial peak load is not simple, it depends on the lay-up configuration in the not chamfered section. The initial part of those crash tests could be not stable with a progressive reduction of the maintained load.

Type "c" is a group of two tubes with different lengths, The influence of the difference between the two tube lengths ($L_2 - L_1$) has been observed. The curve-force displacement for this case has two load peaks. The influence of $L_2 - L_1$ is the amount of the second peak . It has been found that $L_2 - L_1 = 2$ mm in this case leads to the best behaviour. The amount of the two peaks are nearly equals and only a little bit superior to the crash maintained load.

Figure 5.2. Curve type a

Figure 5.3. Curve type b

Figure 5.4. Curve type c

6. RESULTS

The sequence showed in figure 6.1. was runned during the numerical simulations with the mentioned numerical tools. Six deformation stages have been extracted from the numerical simulation of the irreversible part (a composite tube) of the shock absorber.

A great number of parameters have influence in the numerical simulation process, material properties, friction coefficients composite-composite and steel-composite must be defined. Contact surfaces are necessary to define the different contacts, between parts of the splitted tube and between tube and steel plates.

Dyna3d offers ten types of slide surfaces which allow the user to define break surfaces and different kinds of contact. A tied surface with failure is not considered by Abaqus-Explicit v.5.1 code, this means a drawback, and difficult the simulation of the splitted part of the tube.

Figure 6.1. Numerical simulation of crushing of a tube

Numerical simulations can be compared with experimental results as photo 6.1. shows. The same testing conditions were used during the experimental testing and the results proved the powerful and usefulness of these numerical tools.

Photo 6.1. Experimental crushing of a tube.

Another result that can be appointed is that composite materials are feasible to be included in mechanism like this paper is matter. So, a desirable behaviour can be obtained with the use of composite material, as can be seen in figure 6.2. The load and displacement required are satisfied completely by the presented design.

Figure 6.2. Metallic and non metallic comparison.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The method of calculation which has been developed gives a good agreement between theoretical and experimental results. Theoretical simulations help us to reduce the number of experimental testing.

Composite Materials are feasible to be used as a choice in crash absorbing devices because of its stable crash.

A competitive design has been obtained due to its good behaviour and easy manufacturing, so weight saving and low cost are two of the most outstanding characteristics.

References

1. Hull D., *A unified approach to progressive crushing of fibre-reinforced composite tubes*. Composites Science and Technology 40 (1991) 377-421
2. Hull D., *Axial crushing of fibre reinforced composite tubes*. Structural Crashworthiness, Chap.5, ed N.Jones & Wierzbicki. Butterworths, London,1983, pp. 118-35
3. Mamalis A.G., Yuang Y.B. & Viegelahn G.L., *Collapse of thin-wall composite sections subjected to high speed axial loading*. Int.J. of Vehicle Design, vol. 13, nos. 5/6 1992.
4. Mamalis A.G. et al, *On the axial crumpling of fibre-reinforced composite thin-walled conical shells*. Int.J. of Vehicle Design, vol. 12, no. 4, 1991.
5. Farley Gary L. & Jones Robert M., *Crushing Characteristics of Continous Fiber-Reinforced Composite Tubes*. Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 26. No. 1/1992.
6. Farley Gary L. & Jones Robert M., *Analogy for the effect of material and geometrical variables on energy-absorption capability of composite tubes*. Journal of Composite Materials, Vol. 26. No. 1/1992.
7. Farley Gary L., *Energie absorption of composite materials*. Journal of Composite Materials, Vol.17, May 1983.
8. DYNA3D, Whirley Robert G. & Hallquist J. O., *Nonlinear, Explicit, Three-Dimensional Finite Element Code for Solid and Structural Mechanics-User Manual*. May, 1991.Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory.
9. ABAQUS, version 4.9, Hibbit, Karlsson and Sorensen, Inc.
10. ABAQUS/Explicit, version 5.1, Hibbit, Karlsson and Sorensen, Inc.
11. Thorton P.H., Jeryan R.A., *Crash Energy management in composite automotive structures*. Int. Journal Impact Engineering, Vol. 7, No. 2,pp 167-180, 1988.
12. Zukas J.A., Nicholas T., Swift H., Greszczuk L.B., Curran D.R., *Impact Dynamics*. ed John Wiley & Sons, Inc. 1982.
13. Haug E., Fort O., Trameçon A., Watanabe M. & Nakada I., *Numerical Crashworthiness simulation of automotive structures and components made of continuous fiber reinforced composite and sandwich assemblies*. SAE International congress and exposition, Detroit, Michigan. February 25-March 1, 1991.
14. Tsai S. W. *Theory of Composite Design*. Think Composites, 1992.